

OBSERVATION IS THE LEADING METHOD OF NATURE LEARNING IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7402814>

Abstract: this article fully describes the practical importance of observation in the study of nature in preschools.

Key words: observation, nature, activity, method, technology, frontal observation, individual observation.

Follow up — it is to perceive objects and phenomena of nature in natural conditions with the senses without directly interfering with the course of these phenomena. Observation is a complex cognitive activity that involves perception, thinking, and speech, and requires sustained attention. Constant observations in introducing children to nature are of great importance in developing their logical thinking and speech. K.D. Ushinsky says: "True human, intellectual speech consists of correct reasoning, and correct reasoning, as we have shown, comes from real and clear observations, not from anything else." If children are introduced to objects and events in nature in a certain order, their attention and observation, interest in nature, and the desire to know its events will increase.

Observations can be conducted only by drawing attention. By learning to observe, that is, to draw attention to objects and events in a purposeful way, we also develop voluntary attention in them. Correcting misconceptions is much more difficult than creating new ones. Therefore, it is very important for children to have the correct understanding of nature, based on their sensory experiences, even at the age of preschool education. It is necessary to cultivate interest in nature in children, because it can arise even in unhealthy activities. For example, children catch beetles and butterflies and cut off their wings and legs, wondering what they are doing. Or they torture animals and birds and wonder what the result will be. It is necessary to explain to them the interconnectedness of nature, that is, its "golden chain".

Through this, children are given ecological education. "A close relationship with nature teaches interest in knowledge together with observation. This is based on the reflex of speculation and investigation, and its extreme development is a characteristic of a person," believes I.P. Pavlov. "What is this?", "Why?", "How?" endless questions such as

In this case, the teacher should try to involve the children in finding answers to the questions. When organizing observations in different age groups of children of preschool age, the educator uses its various types.

Methodology of conducting systematic and episodic observations.

Observations can be short-term and long-term in terms of duration and character. A more complex type of observation - long-term observations - is used to accumulate knowledge about the growth and development of plants and animals, seasonal changes in nature. In this case, children have to compare the observed state of the object with the previous one. Observation is also organized in order to determine the condition of things based on certain signs (for example, watering a flower based on its leaves, changing water based on the state of

the water in the aquarium, or depending on the track in the snow, which bird's track it is, distinguishing ripe or unripe fruits based on their color). This type of observation helps children to develop the skills of analyzing natural phenomena, comparing some information, and drawing simpler conclusions. Due to the complexity of the content of comparisons and long-term observations, it is used in preschool, secondary, senior and preparatory groups. During these observations, the process of analyzing, comparing, drawing conclusions improves in children. According to the content of the observations and the goal set by the educator, excursions, walks, and activities in the nature corner are organized with plants and animals, weather, and the work of adults in nature. In the process of short-term observation, children learn to distinguish the shape, color, size, structure, spatial location, surface character of objects, and when they get to know animals, they learn the nature of movement and the sounds they emit. This type of observation includes, for example, the occurrence of snow or rain, the formation of a rainbow. In all cases, observation should develop children's high mental activity, encourage them to think, find answers to the questions, as well as develop their interests and educate them to be careful with nature.

Educator preparation for observation. The choice of object is of great importance in the organization of observation. The chosen object must be in good condition, that is, the plant must not wither, the varieties must not be packed, the animal must be trained, healthy, and not afraid of children. If the observation is in the corner of nature, the object should be well lit, the light should fall from the side so that it is convenient to approach it. Children can feed, pet, and play with the animals while watching their movements. It is necessary for animals to behave freely and move freely. For this, it is advisable for children to sit comfortably in the corner of nature.

Manage tracking. If the teacher is conducting the observation for the first time, he watches the children for at least 1-2 minutes in order to satisfy their interests and create a first impression of what is being observed. In the process of controlling observation, the educator uses various methods - questions and assignments suitable for the children's age, holding things, comparing, and playing. While organizing the observation, the teacher must provide the necessary information and distinguish the important features of the observed object. In order to arouse children's interest in observation and aesthetic perception of observed objects, the educator uses poems, riddles, and in older age groups, reading works of art. When observing the animals, the educator observes consistency and draws the children's attention to "What is it doing?" "How's it going?" "What is he eating?" "How is he eating?" "What is his body covered with?" "What are his legs like - long or short?" "What are his eyes (shape, color)?" focuses on the behavior of animals using questions like Observing plants begins with identifying and distinguishing their brightest, most visible signs. It can be the flower of a plant or its brightly colored leaves, sometimes a stem (for example, a cactus). After that, the main characteristics of the external structure of the plant - size, shape, stem (or body), leaves, flowers, etc. are considered in order. Such consistency is necessary due to the fact that the attention of children of preschool age is not stable enough, and in many ways they are involuntary. However, at the end of the training, it is necessary to generalize the result of the ideas that appeared during the observation process. The educator uses different methods of giving tasks, "Tell me, how did you know?" How is it different?" It helps the children to develop their speech through observation with questions and assignments. In all cases, when the educator organizes observation, he should observe consistency in moving from one

specific task to another, from facts to connections, from collecting ideas to comparing them, and then drawing conclusions. Then children develop logical thinking. In each observation, it is necessary to solve a small, specific task of introducing children to nature. Therefore, it is necessary to connect each observation with the previous one.

Episodic observations - divide into "pieces". Such observation is carried out when changes in the development of plants are clearly visible. The teacher advises the children to observe the plant and note its signs (seeing the emergence of the first leaves, the emergence of the seed coat of the plant). In the final observation, children should restore the whole picture of the observed plant development. This observation can be organized on the basis of a diary, various pictures, herbariums, and in large age groups, graphic tables.

Observation using handouts. These observations are conducted starting from middle age groups. Organization of such observation is much more complicated than observation of a single object. In this case, the educator is required to be able to divide his attention, to be able to organize the movement of the children, and the children must strictly follow all the instructions of the educator, listen to each other, compare the observations of others with their own observations. . This method of observation has great developmental value. Children will have the opportunity to improve their academic skills using various research activities. This, in turn, helps them to form more accurate ideas. Plants and their leaves, fruits, seeds, branches, as well as vegetables and fruits are widely used as distribution material. Every child and educator who participated in the observation has a handout, and during the observation, the educator asks the children questions and arranges to check things. Then compares the received images and teaches children to draw conclusions. During the observation process, the educator ensures high activity of all children.

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